

INTERPRETATION OF REFLECTIONS ABOUT EDUCATION AND LEARNING IN THE HERITAGE OF MAKHMUDXO'JA BEHBUDI

Djumaeva Sh.S.

Teacher of NEO, Economics and Pedagogical University

Sirodzhiddinov R.A.

1-st year student of the Economics and Pedagogical University

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The name of the national hero of the people of Turkestan, public, cultural and educational figure, the first Uzbek playwright, great journalist, writer, translator Mahmudhodja Behbudi is known and known not only to the intelligentsia of Turkestan, but also beyond its borders. countries and in many countries in Asia and Europe. Therefore, his life and work have been under the attention of historians, literary scholars, lawyers, art critics and the general public for almost a century. His social and creative activities are studied by specialists in various fields, and his literary heritage is published.

Behbudi is the greatest representative of the Turkestan socio-political movement on the threshold of the twentieth century, the founder of a new era of Uzbek culture. Behbudi was of the opinion that only when a nation understands itself can it intervene in social and political issues on an equal basis with others. Appreciating the national culture, history and traditions of the Uzbek people in his socio-political views, the thinker notes with great pity in his views that the people, devoid of knowledge and sleepless, will get used to all kinds of injustice and oppression. He will not be able to actively fight for his freedom and independence and will continue to look indifferently at the destruction of his national dignity. He recognizes that deprivation, poverty and humiliation are all the fruits and results of ignorance and lack of discipline.

Behbudi understands that one of the most important factors in getting rid of dependence and saving the nation from destruction is the awakening of the people of Turkestan from the sleep of carelessness. In this regard, in Padarkush he speaks on behalf of Zieli: "Now is a new and different time. At this time, people without knowledge and skills will lose their wealth, husband and tools day by day. For this we must try to educate the Muslims, although our noble religion obliges us to study all types of knowledge from the cradle to the grave. This decision is Shariah. We Muslims, especially in this era, need two classes of scientists: one is a religious scholar, the other is a modern scientist" [1]. Reflecting on independence in his works, Adib rejects any violence. In his opinion, violence is immoral and therefore inhumane. In general, when our grandfathers, who fought for independence, including the younger ones, think

about the future, we are sure that the main goal of your ideas about achieving independence is the desire to achieve freedom and prosperity of the country, as well as its independence. Mahmudhoja Behbudi's genius was so keen that almost 140 years ago he identified the problems that we are now beginning to solve thanks to independence.

In the history of the peoples of Turkestan, moral education has always developed and improved in the activities of representatives of Jadidism. The practical significance of studying their thoughts on morality and ethics lies in the fact that in addition to moral education, they also reflect the ancient customs and traditions of our people. For example, in the educational and moral views of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the qualities acquired by knowledge, truth found in the internal and external appearance, behavior created by the mind, and health, which is more important than property, were considered the main thing. The requirements of a person who needs to be a spiritually mature person. These requirements are considered an important resource in nurturing courage, correctness, justice, fidelity, honesty, generosity, mercy, and humanitarian qualities in raising a comprehensively developed personality. The great school of Enlightenment and its foundations were considered as a whole and achieved many successes along the way. These principles are reflected in the books and manuals he created for modern schools. The textbooks created by Behbudi in a modern spirit became very popular in their time and some of them were republished[2].

Behbudi considered modern schools to be a reliable tool for making people literate and enlightened. He viewed the press as an instrument for disseminating education and used its power effectively. Behbudi's educational views and issues of the struggle for the harmony of education were directly reflected on the pages of the Samarkand newspaper and the Oyna magazine, which he founded as a publisher and editor.

Mahmudhodja Behbudi approached the issues of pedagogy differently. Since he was not only a leading publicist and public figure of his time, but also an excellent trainer, teacher and psychologist, he deeply studied the nature of the child and included science in educational programs that give the child complex knowledge. Subjects of study included etiquette, geography, natural science, language, jurisprudence, geometry and some modern knowledge. Its educational system includes the following: 1) Intellectual education. 2) Moral education. 3) Religious education. 4) Aesthetic education. 5) Legal education. Behbudi, speaking about the development of human thinking, emphasized the role of

intellectual education. Mental education. as he pointed out, this is done through the school of elevation of the mind. Therefore, in this regard, he took the issue of worldly knowledge seriously. Studying geography, geometry, mathematics, natural sciences and foreign languages is one of the keys to understanding the world [3].

The New Method School, founded by Mahmudhoja Behbudi, is distinguished by systematic and consistent teaching. It is clearly seen that it is built on a deep scientific basis and that theory is inextricably linked with practice. His ideas on the development of science and education of youth are considered a valuable treasure of his time and modernity. His thoughts in this area complement each other and, with the attention of the essence, lead a person to perfection.

In his pedagogical views, Mahmudhoja Behbudi not only paid serious attention to the education of boys, but also had a positive attitude towards the issue of women's education. Behbudi hired his daughter Parveen Khan as a teacher, first in the modern method and then in French, and taught this science very well. Parvin Khan has been teaching this subject to young people for many years in the village of Kazikorgan near the city of Samarkand. Behbudi shows the role of family and school in raising healthy children, emphasizing the need to pay attention to their physical and hygienic education. Such views are expressed in his article "Family Security" (Preserving the Health of the Family). He says that children must be taught to be clean from a very early age and protected from all sorts of bad vices. He says that children should not be allowed to read romantic Fasals from an early age [4]. It should be recognized that Mahmudhuja Behbudi seriously struggled with the issue of children's education and showed ways to get rid of problems in this work. Through these considerations we can deeply understand that every parent should not be indifferent to the education of today's young generation and that their future must inevitably be based on national education.

In conclusion, we can say that the memory of Mahmudhoja Behbudi as a patriot who gave his life for independence will remain forever for this people and the Motherland. The ideas and activities of the great educator Mahmudhodji Behbudi remain forever in our history, his dreams and hopes are being realized with the honor of independence.

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